

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Olaitan**FIRST NAME:** Gbenga**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

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List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-6)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 25-26)
4. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 56-61)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2021, 49-55)
7. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2021, 6-7)

PATH TO BETTER ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Coming from a country colonized by Great Britain and therefore an *anglo-phone* citizen, my academic life was imparted using the English Language. I studied in English Language at primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions. My experience as a Biochemist who had worked in different pharmaceutical industries improved my writing skills. As sales manager and quality assurance manager, I wrote reports on sales appraisal and clinical meetings daily. I also did PowerPoint presentations in different hospitals. Despite all these past engagements, after going through the ACA-401D course pack, I still have a lot to learn in academic writing, business reporting, and general presentation. There is a saying in local folk tales that "*if you do not go to other people's father's farm, you can wrongly assume that your father's farm is the biggest.*"¹ The resources available in ACA-401D are very robust, and I have learned many things to sharpen my ability in academic writing. The coursepack explained that academic writing must be evidence-based and not emotion laden; this is correct because emotions can sometimes mislead our sense of judgment.

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The exposition on plagiarism provided in the ACA-401D coursepack is re-sounding and very important in this critical level of academics. I have learned how to avoid plagiarism one hundred percent. What I have acquired concerning in-text citation,

references and footnote are all inestimable. Education on *paraphrasing*, the Chicago manual of style and Turabian's manual for writers of term papers, Zotero referencing, and Grammarly tutorials are all of great value to writing a better essay. The rules of thumb for writing a response paper in particular and academic writing, in general, is what I will always value in my roadmap towards academic success.

2) IMPROVING YOUR WRITING SKILLS

Chapter one of ACA-401D period one coursepack elaborately thought about improving and becoming a better essay writer. I learned in the course pack that an academic essay aims to persuade a reader of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2021, 1). Graham, Harris, and Chambers corroborated this in a charge to teachers that "*the identification of evidence-based practices in writing also provides you and your colleagues with a set of general principles for teaching writing*" (Graham and Harris 2016, 2). If an academic essay answers a question, it must be free of fallacies and unfounded information; it must be evidence-based. Writing down just what you know about a topic is not enough to make a good academic essay. Analyzing, then answering the essay question is central (EUCLID 2021, 1). A thesis statement should answer the research question adequately; input from comprehensive research and personal knowledge ensures this. Planning the research analysis is much more important than the initial thought.

Researching provides the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (EUCLID 2021, 2). In researching, you must make notes, think critically, and organize your ideas into steps convenient to follow. Do not include only evidence that agrees with your position; opposing views are of essence to determine the superior and more convincing ones. From the coursepack, I learned from Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma the basic principles of structuring our essay into Introduction, body, and conclusion using essay paragraphs. One great knowledge I have acquired in this course pack is putting the essay aside for a few days: I have never done this before. Doing this makes one consider the essay with a fresh eye (EUCLID 2021, 3), which allows for editing. In an essay, 'A path to better writing,' Steve Graham and Karen R. Harris opined that "*good writing is not a gift. It is forged by desire, practice, and assistance from others. You can play a central role in this development by teaching writing effectively*" (Graham and Harris 2016, 1). Assistance from others means one must do research, organize and analyze the points to be evidence-based; this is critical to every essay writing.

3) PLAGIARISM

One of the holy books says, "*In the beginning was the Word, the Word was with God, and the Word was God*" (Book of John 1:1, Holy Bible King James Version). A man's words represent him, and it is his honor. Plagiarism is like kidnapping a person; it is therefore evil. It is taking credit that does not belong to you. When writing papers, one of the most important things to avoid is plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5). "Plagiarism is an issue

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of concern in the academic world. It is estimated to make up a substantial number of serious deviations from good research practice? (Helgesson and Eriksson 2015, 2).

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One must have a list of work cited at the end of a book or article using the author's name, date, title, place of publication and publisher. I was also pleased to see the instruction in the course materials calling for the balance of evidence by not only including those that agree with us but also the ones coming from different authors that might be against our views (EUCLID 2021, 2). The scientific community in healthcare welcomes ideas from all researchers of different disciplines. Listening to different voices, including studying negative results obtained in previous research, is very important for us to evaluate in a logical and scientific way. Acknowledge the source using in-text citation and finally link it up to the list of work cited, known as a reference list, which is the last section of the paper.

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It is gratifying to know the minds of Euclid university faculty on plagiarism. One can plagiarize basically in two ways: using the word of a source without quotation marks, even with a footnote, or taking ideas from a source without footnoting the source (EUCLID 2021, 16). I have always advocated against any form of cheating, even in my professional career, because it is improper and unethical.

4) STYLE SHEET

There are rules on organizing and presenting academic papers, pieces, or published content in academic writing. It is the standard set for designing, writing, and formatting document. It is like a sheet containing all the relevant guidelines for writing an academic essay. A style guide may set out rules in punctuation, capitalization, citation, formatting, et cetera.

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to some aspects of writing style that need to be consistent. They are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, business writing, journalism, and copywriting (EUCLID 2021, 24). The use of the style is to the writer's advantage because it ensures consistency in the write-up. There are several style elements, but the voice and English language preferences caught my attention in the ACA-401 course pack.

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a) VOICE PREFERENCE

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An essay can reflect either passive voice or active voice. The recommended voice in academic writing is active; I cannot entirely agree with this. Passive voice has a sentence in which the subject is acted upon by the object, which means the subject is the receiver of verb's action. In active voice, a sentence has a subject that acts upon the verb. Is it always correct to say that an active voice has a strong, direct, and clear tone? Remember, active and passive voice expresses the same ideas differently; this means that passive voice is not

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inherently wrong. Passive voice is good when you want to emphasize the recipient of the action. Use active voice unless you specifically need to use the passive (EUCLID 2021, 17), it means there are instances when passive voice is good for use.

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b) ENGLISH USAGE PREFERENCE

Factors like population, wealth, publishing industries, global mass media, popular culture, and political and economic position have made American English more recognized and accepted than British English (EUCLID 2021, 27). There are many differences between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE). Some words have the exact spelling but different pronunciations, for example, schedule. Other words have the same pronunciation but different spelling plough/plow.

In Nigeria, most people use a combination of SAE and SBE; this makes editing an essay difficult, particularly as you want to conform to SAE as a recommendation for a response paper. In many places, to use SAE or SBE, there is disagreement in the use of grammar. In honorifics, Nigerians use both SAE and SBE to apply period to Mr or Mrs. This is the same in applying period before or after quotation marks; in SAE, periods come before the final quotation mark. In a large collection of nouns, I am used to assuming the subject is singular. The statement: 'the government are acting like themselves again' is therefore wrong. Academic style means using logical connectors so that there is a flow in your paper as a writer (EUCLID 2021, 12).

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5) CHICAGO (TURABIAN) MANUAL OF STYLE

In this section, I want to discuss citation and formatting styles in academic writing. In the checklist to sending response paper, page [two](#), it was directed that the paper must comply with EUCLID guidelines and the right style for essays. The 17th edition of the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) shows the writing and citation styles used in publishing. CMS is the preferred formatting and style guideline for most disciplines. The Turabian citation style is a simpler version of CMS, and it is mostly for students who are not publishing their papers. The academic writing style organizes the paper in tone, diction, language, punctuation, and citation. Chicago manual of style (CMS), 2003 and Kate Turabian's [Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations](#) are best in editing students' essays; this is why EUCLID recommends it as the editing tool for response papers (EUCLID 2021, 24).

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At the M.Sc level, I used the American Psychological Association (APA) style, which has many similarities with CMS. I have certain reservations in CMS usage because citations using APA are more streamlined and uniform; it makes papers easier to read and understand. APA style is helpful to cite sources in psychology education and social sciences. This allows readers to know what to look for. Judy Reeves made a profound statement that *"Write what matters. If you do not care about what you write, neither will*

your readers" (Benard 2012, 1). Chicago (Turabian) style allows the use of footnotes and endnotes while APA does not. Footnote lists more information about the source. Footnotes should be on a page or must begin on the page where the citations exist. (Indicated by a superscript numeral in the text (EUCLID 2021, 51). Footnotes can create a better understanding of the essay and, consequently, "the use of *Op. Cit* and *Loc. Cit* commonly used in scholarly reference is now discouraged (EUCLID 2021, 51). It means the need to refer readers to a particular place in the essay is no longer required. Another fundamental style for academic writing is the heading style; it results in a well-organized essay. The "style" menu on the Microsoft word document provides you with the option of using different headings for the response paper. All major headings should have "RP Head 1" applied. Heading two to have "RP Head 2", heading three to have "RP Head 3", text in the body of the essay to have "RP Normal", quotations to have "RP Quote," the title of the paper, and title of reference to have "RP Title" and the reference list to have "RP reference."

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6) THE BLUEPRINT LANGUAGE

Latin is the blueprint language for many other languages. More than sixty percent of English words came from Latin, and it helps the English language to have a rich vocabulary. Latin is a key to Romance, Spanish, French, Italian and Portuguese languages. Latin is the language of western civilization and international communication. This language is not dead as Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliography, and essay writing. Business, formal and technical writing use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by readers (EUCLID 2021, 56). We use Latin words daily; it is part of our day-to-day conversation. I was surprised to discover that 'plagiarize' was derived from Latin words '*plagiarius*,' which means kidnappers. It means stolen words rather than stolen children. <http://www.merriam-webster.com>

There are many exciting abbreviations that man cannot do without, such as "A.M" and "P.M," which means *ante meridiem* and *post meridiem*, respectively; this has helped us separate morning and night hours. *Et al.* has been a helpful abbreviation in academic writing to avoid listing many names or many authors; the convenience this offers to writers is priceless. As a young biochemist, I cannot forget the type of confidence that usually overwhelms me when I use the abbreviation '*in-situ*' in the laboratory when studying albino rat internal organs; this means studying them in the original positions. We used terms like '*in-vivo*' for biological processes occurring within a living organism and '*in-vitro*' as biological processes occurring outside the living organism.

Latin words are essential for English vocabularies to the extent that "*high school student should be led to recognize that so long as the English language lives, the Latin language cannot die*," (Bracke and Bradshaw 2020, 2). Latin words and abbreviations will always be valuable in the legal, medical science, art, and social science professions.

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7) EASY REFERENCING

Referencing is an essential integral part of any academic writing; this is why Zotero reference manager is a valuable tool for scholarly writing. After installing Zotero and Zotero connectors, you need to create an effective reference library that one can fetch from when doing reference. One should endeavor to add a reference to Zotero.

The almost thirteen-minute video on how to use Zotero explains three methods to add a reference to Zotero. It can be manually; reference can also be done with an identifier or by using Zotero connectors to add the reference. For example, an Identifier code is at the top of each article in a journal article (documents). Copy the code, select add item by identifier option, paste the code, and press enter on the keyboard. After this, you can type the title, add author, add a publication, add volume, add page number, and then save. This method is a lot quicker and gives more information about the documents. For me, adding references with the use of an identifier is the best. When I tried the three methods, it was the easiest and most convenient for me to use. More so, the exact web page of the document can be opened in your browser using this method.

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8) CONCLUSION

The ACA-40ID course pack is very rich for someone ready to fine-tune his academic writing skills. All essential things to know in writing an almost impeccable essay are available in the write-up and the videos. I have learned the importance of an evidence-based essay and that essay should not just be based on what one knows already but must be researched. To write a scholarly essay, one must avoid plagiarism like the plague, and the reference is better done using Zotero referencing. The difference between "*that*" and "*which*." is now known. "*That*" precedes only restrictive phrases, while "*which*" usually precedes non-restrictive phrases (EUCLID 2021, 19). Now, I know how to use "*I*" and "*me*" correctly. The style guide: Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and Turabian Manual for Writers, which EUCLID recommends, is good because I found it better than APA, which I have been using. CMS allows the use of footnotes, which makes essays better organized and easy to browse through. The CMS also provides a detailed explanation regarding formatting guidelines. What gladdens my mind the most was the video on Grammarly where grammar, punctuations, overused and repeated words, passive sentences, and plagiarism can be corrected. It was made clear that it is better to place documents directly on Grammarly rather than on google document. Offering ACA-40ID as the first course is strategic because it has improved my academic writing skills in the program's roadmap.

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